

D 7.2

Sharing findings and the Observatory (final version)

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Abstract	Intersect Observatory is the place on the website where HRJust communicates and engages with Civil Society, Academia as well as Public Authorities by disseminating and communicating its output (tools, toolkit, infographics), reports and academic publications.
Keywords	Human Rights Justifications (HRJs), Dissemination and Communication, Research, Civil Society, outputs, reports, academic publications

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Executive Summary

This is a shared Deliverable between UGOT and NCKU where NCKU has provided the programming and the structure for the website, building and the layout. UGOT has provided the content and aesthetics of the website. The Intersect Observatory is placed within the main HRJust website. The Deliverable illustrates how the website and Observatory share and promote findings and materials generated by HRJust.

The main HRJust website

Here is where the general information about the project is presented. It is organised by our themes: Covid, Migration and Climate Crisis, and sets out the scope: Sweden, Finland, India, Ukraine and Taiwan, as well as the beneficiaries.

<p><u>HRJust & Climate</u></p> <p>Studies how States use human rights to justify climate policies. It assesses whether these justifications strengthen accountability or leave people unprotected, and develops recommendations for fair and rights-based climate governance.</p> <p>READ MORE</p>		
<p><u>Complex Intersectionality</u></p> <p>HRJust has developed a concept for analyzing gender and intersectionality through Covid, Migration and Climate</p>		

Countries

hrjust.wpcomstaging.com

HRJust
HUMAN RIGHTS JUSTIFICATIONS

About Publications News Events Search

ABOUT HRJUST

Human Rights Justification (HRJust) describes situations in which States invoke human rights to legitimize their own policies and decisions. Although often presented as rights-protective, such justifications can also function as tools of governance, expanding or normalising state power.

This shift exposes a regulatory gap: existing human rights frameworks are designed to protect individuals from the State, yet they offer limited guidance when human rights are instead used by the State to justify its actions.

RESEARCH FOCUS

Our research focuses on State use of Human Rights Justifications in the areas of **Covid-19, migration, and climate**, across five country contexts: **Sweden, Finland, Taiwan, India, and Ukraine**.

EU FINLAND UKRAINE SWEDEN TAIWAN INDIA

The Funding Agency and Beneficiaries

PARTNERS

HRJust, A Horizon EU Funded Project.

Examines how States use Human Rights Justifications to explain and defend their actions and decisions.

Contact Us

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The Main Website contains information about Events and News

News

News – HRJust

HRJust Early Alert — April to August: Public Consultations in Sweden That May Affect Human Rights
April 20, 2026

A new round of public consultations is open, highlighting government inquiries and proposals that may have implications for human rights in Sweden. This curated list points to current state inquiries where civil society voices are both relevant and needed. Even if your organization has not been formally invited to respond, you still have the opportunity...

New Publication Exploring Russia's Use of Human Rights Justifications in Defense of its Invasion of Ukraine
April 11, 2026

Human rights are conventionally conceptualised as normative safeguards that enable individuals to hold States accountable. However, an emerging line of inquiry examines a more complex dynamic: the invocation of human rights by States themselves as justificatory tools for their own actions. In this chapter, Maria Grahn-Farley develops the concept of human rights justifications, referring to...

Highlights from the Nordic Rule of Law Forum 2025
December 12, 2025

Last week, the HRJust project had the privilege of co-hosting the Nordic Rule of Law Forum 2025 together with Civil Rights Defenders. The forum brought together researchers, legal experts, civil society actors, and policymakers to engage in critical discussions on the rule of law and the evolving role of human rights in state practice. Researchers...

Events

Events - HRJust

Highlights from the Nordic Rule of Law Forum 2025

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HRJust Workshop at Stockholm University: Exploring Human Rights Justifications in Practice

December 10, 2025

Last week, the HRJust project hosted a full-day workshop at Stockholm University, bringing together researchers, civil society actors, and international partners to explore the implications of states invoking human rights as justification for policy and governance. Participants included collaborators from Academia Sinica and National Cheng Kung University (NCKU), alongside representatives from civil society organisations and...

Seminar on Human Rights Protection in Sweden in a Global Context

December 2, 2025

On 10 November, the HRJust project hosted a seminar examining recent developments in human rights protection in Sweden and their connection to broader global trends of democratic decline. The event featured a keynote presentation by John Stauffer, Legal Director and Deputy Executive Director of Civil Rights Defenders. In his talk, "The State of Human Rights..."

The Intersect Observatory

HRJust - Human Rights Justifications

INTERSECT OBSERVATORY

GALLERY

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Supported by the European Union

REPORTS

HRJust Early Alert — April to August: Public Consultations in Sweden That May Affect Human Rights

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[Read more](#)

ACADEMIC PUBLICATIONS

Maria Grahn-Farley. How to Counter Attempts by Authoritarian States to Redefine the Concept of Human Rights: Russia's Use of Human Righ...

April 11, 2026

Abstract Human rights justification refers to when States activate human rights to justify their decisions and actions. Normally, it is the individual who invokes a human right against the State but with human rights justifications, it is the State that invokes human rights for its...

[Read more](#)

Gallery

The Gallery is designed for Civil Society and Website visitors who want a general overview of the research topic: Human Rights Justifications.

WELCOME TO THE HRJUST GALLERY!

This is where research steps out of the paper and into view. Here you'll find infographics, toolkits, behind-the-scenes snapshots, and other visual materials that bring our work on human rights justifications to life.

Think of it as our working space made visible — where ideas are translated, tested, and shared in more accessible forms. Whether you're here to explore, learn, or simply get a closer look at how our research unfolds, the Gallery is designed to make complex questions easier to see, understand, and engage with.

How do States defend and legitimize their actions through human rights?

Infographics to illustrate with examples and pictures how States are using HRJs:

> <

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Intersect Observatory holds all the Publications generated by the project

Under the “Publications” tab is all the output uploaded where comparisons between research results that can be generally applicable and research results that are specific to a time and place. One example is the Taiwanese Focus Groups studies conducted on COVID-19. These are both place based and time specific as they give general insights on the limitations of socially constructed identity theory. The large number of reports authored in the project address: How States defend and legitimize its actions through human rights; the publications provide analysis over the role of geopolitics, especially to be noted are the publications on Ukraine and Taiwan as being rich on geopolitical analysis. The role of EU is described in several of the EU focused reports and academic publications presented in the Intersect Observatory, especially the reports and publications on migration.

All the Reports

Examples of reports listed on the Intersect Observatory website:

Focus Group Interview with People Who Underwent Quarantine, Ching-Yun Tai & Shun-Ling Chen

January 2, 2025

As part of our civil society engagement, the WP4 Taiwan team organised three focus groups examining how pandemic governance in Taiwan disproportionately impacted certain social groups: frontline health professionals, pilots, and individuals who experienced quarantine during COVID-19. The third group brought together people who had undergone quarantine, offering first-hand perspectives on isolation measures, enforcement practices,...

Focus Group Interview with Pilots, Ching-Yun Tai & Shun-Ling Chen

December 16, 2024

The HRJust Taiwan team continues its focus group discussions to deepen understanding of how pandemic governance in Taiwan has disproportionately affected different social groups. This time, the focus is on pilots and their experiences during the COVID-19 period. Read the full report from the focus group interview below.

Next page »

And all the Academic Publications

Examples of Academic Publications:

Laura Carlson, 'The Changing Paradigm of Human Rights Justifications: Challenges for Civil Society'. *Zbornik znanstvenih razprav (Ljubljana Law Review)* 85 (2025): 135–164

February 20, 2026

ABSTRACT This article scrutinises the evolving paradigm of human rights justifications (HRJs) and the growing complexities encountered by civil society when states invoke human rights to legitimise restrictive migration policies. Originally conceived as a shield to protect individuals from state power, human rights have increasingly been appropriated by states as instruments of governance, particularly in...

Catarina Milo, 'Environmental and Human Rights Justifications in Investment Arbitration: Probing the Limits of ISDS for the Adjudication of Climate-Related Disputes', *Journal of World Investment & Trade* (2025)

May 30, 2025

Abstract This article examines the capacity of investment arbitration to analyze cases concerning complex issues of public international law, focusing on the challenges connected to climate-related cases. Through the analysis of arbitral awards involving environmental and human rights justifications, this article evaluates ways in which non-economic arguments may be effectively raised in investor-State dispute settlement...

Grahn-Farley, Maria, *Child Rights, Legal Theory and Social Advocacy* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2024)

January 21, 2025

This publication by HRJust Project Coordinator, Professor, Maria Grahn-Farley explores how child rights are evolving in today's shifting political and legal landscape, offering both a foundational overview and a critical perspective on their role in society. *Child Rights, Legal Theory and Social Advocacy* offers both an introduction to the field of child rights and a...

The website address: <https://hrjust.org/>

LinkedIn account

The screenshot shows the LinkedIn profile page for 'Human Rights Justifications'. The page is divided into three main sections: a left-hand navigation menu, a central 'Activity' feed, and a right-hand 'Post highlights' section.

Left-hand navigation menu:

- ust logo
- Human Rights Justifications
- Enhance your Page
- 424 followers
- + Create
- View as member
- Dashboard
- Page posts
- Analytics
- Feed
- Activity (highlighted)
- Inbox

Activity section:

Activity
Keep track of the activity around your page

All | Comments | Mentions | Reactions | More ▾

Activity 1d: Nino Janiashvili and 13 others reacted to your company's update
How can research move beyond analysis and actually shape policy? HRJust's Pathway Towards Impact shows how a...
HRJust's Pathway Towards Impact

Activity 2d: **EMPLOYEE ACTIVITY** Wasan Mohamed Osman commented on your company's update
Dr Raj Kumar Thank you!! 😊
How can research move beyond analysis and actually shape policy? HRJust's Pathway Towards Impact shows...
Respond

Post highlights section:

Post highlights ⓘ
In the last 30 days

Most engagement

HRJust's Pathway Towards Impact
14 reactions · 8 comments

Get up to 170,000 additional impressions. **Boost**

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